

Evaluation of Van der Waals dipole-dipole and dipole-quadrupole energies and crystal energies in copper, silver and thallium halides

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Manuscript received 17 August 2006, revised 29 November 2006, accepted 29 November 2006

Abstract : The Slater-Kirkwood variational method is applied to estimate the Van der Waals dipole-dipole (vdw) and dipole-quadrupole co-efficients for ion-pair interaction in copper, silver and thallium halide crystals. In the analysis of crystal binding based on the interionic force model, the contributions arising from the vdw dipole-dipole and dipole-quadrupole interactions and the short-range repulsive interactions of the type of Born-Mayer, Hellmann and Ali-Hasan have been taken into account. The calculated values of the crystal energy using the Ali-Hasan repulsive potential agree closely with the experimental value.

Keywords : Van der Waals energy, dipole-dipole energy, dipole-quadrupole energy, crystal energy.

The aim of the present study is to examine the validity of the simple combination rules

$$C_{+-} = (C_{++} C_{--})^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

$$D_{+-} = (D_{++} D_{--})^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

using our Van der Waals co-efficient for copper, silver and thallium halide crystals. Here the usual symbols C_{+-} , C_{++} and C_{--} stand for dipole-dipole constants for cation-anion, cation-cation and anion-anion ion pairs respectively. Similarly D_{+-} , D_{++} and D_{--} are dipole-quadrupole constants for cation-anion, cation-cation and anion-anion respectively. The results obtained are presented in Table 1 which reveals the validity of the combination rules (1-2) for our new vdw co-efficients of copper, silver and thallium halides.

Crystal energy :

The suitability of the new values of Van der Waals potentials can be judged by calculating the crystal energy, W , which is expressed as :

$$W = Ae^2/r - C/r^6 - D/r^8 + V_{sr}(r) \quad (3)$$

where A is the Madelung constant, $V_{sr}(r)$ is the short-range repulsive interaction arising from the overlap of two combining ions and r is the interionic distance between the ion-pair. We have applied Born-Mayer¹, Hellmann² and Ali-Hasan^{3,4} short range repulsive potentials in eq. (3) to compute the values of crystal energy for copper, silver and thallium halides.

The reason for selecting these models is due to their

Table 1. The Van der Waals co-efficients showing the validity of combination rules eqs. (1) and (2)

Crystal	C_{+-} 10^{-60} erg cm ⁶	$(C_{++} C_{--})^{1/2}$ 10^{-60} erg cm ⁶	D_{+-} 10^{-76} erg cm ⁸	$(D_{++} D_{--})^{1/2}$ 10^{-76} erg cm ⁸
CuCl	171.9	177.4	95.9	92.6
CuBr	252.0	257.6	131.6	128.4
CuI	334.6	351.0	204.0	194.0
AgF	87.7	87.7	40	40
AgCl	246	251.4	141	137.4
AgBr	360	365.1	193.8	190.5
AgI	480	497.4	299.5	287.8
TlCl	417.9	418.2	299.0	298.8
TlBr	604.8	607.4	416.8	414.2
TlI	828	827.4	626	625.7

suitability in evaluating the molecular state properties as well crystalline state properties of diatomic ionic crystals. Secondly, the choice of using the Hellmann and Ali-Hasan repulsive potentials lies on the fact that these two potentials satisfy the fundamental physical requirements of an ideal potential. The short-range repulsive potentials $V_{sr}(r)$ can be expressed as

$$\text{Born-Mayer : } S \exp(-r/\rho) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Hellman : } (S_1/r) \exp(-r/\rho_1) \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Ali-Hasan : } S_2/r^2 \exp(-br^n) \quad (6)$$

where S_i is the repulsive strength parameter and ρ_i and b are the repulsive softness parameters. These parameters are generally determined by applying the crystal stability and compressibility conditions

$$(dW/dr)_{r=r_0} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$(d^2W/dr^2)_{r=r_0} = 9V/\beta_0 \quad (8)$$

Here r_0 is the equilibrium interionic distance and β_0 is the isothermal compressibility. V is the unit cell volume. The input data r_0 and β_0 are taken from the source⁵⁻⁷.

The dipole-dipole and dipole-quadrupole constants C and D are expressed as

$$C = S_{+-} C_{+-} + S_{++} C_{++} + S_{--} C_{--} \quad (9)$$

$$D = T_{+-} D_{+-} + T_{++} D_{++} + T_{--} D_{--} \quad (10)$$

where S_{ij} and T_{ij} are the lattice sums which are taken from Tosi⁸. Here i and j are subscripts for positive and negative ions respectively. Of the various methods for calculating the values of C_{ij} and D_{ij} available in literature, May⁹, Mayer and Levy⁶ and Bakhshi *et al.*¹⁰ have taken the London-Marganau (LM) theory based on the perturbation treatment to evaluate the values of C_{ij} and D_{ij} for copper, silver and thallium halide crystals. In the present paper we have applied Slater-Kirkwood variational theory¹¹ which contains the least number of uncertainty to evaluate C_{ij} and D_{ij} for copper, silver and thallium halides.

Results and discussion

The results of computations carried out in the present study are reported in Tables 1-3. Table 2 contains the values of effective number of electrons in the ions of s -block, p -block and d -block elements of the periodic table and other input data. Values of dipole-dipole and dipole-quadrupole co-efficients for ion pairs i.e. Cu^+-Cu^+ , Ag^+-Ag^+ , Tl^+-Tl^+ , Cu^+-X^- , Ag^+-X^- , Tl^+-X^- , $-\text{X}^-$ (where

Table 2. Values of valencies (z), number of electrons present in first (N_1), second (N_2) outermost shells and the effective number of electrons (N) for ions of s -block, p -block and d -block elements of the periodic table

Ions	Z	N_1	N_2	N
<i>s</i> -Block :				
Li^+	1	2	-	3
Be^+	1	3	-	4
Na^+	1	8	2	11
K^+	1	8	8	17
Rb^+	1	8	18	27
Cs^{2+}	1	8	18	27
Mg^{2+}	2	8	2	12
Ca^{2+}	2	8	8	18
Sr^{2+}	2	8	18	28
Ba^{2+}	2	8	18	28
<i>p</i> -Block :				
Tl^+	1	2	18	21
F^-	1	8	2	9
Cl^-	1	8	8	15
Br^-	1	8	18	25
I^-	1	8	18	25
O^{2-}	2	8	2	8
S^{2-}	2	8	8	14
Se^{2-}	2	8	18	24
Te^{2-}	2	8	18	24
<i>d</i> -Block :				
Mn^{2+}	2	13	8	19
Fe^{2+}	2	14	8	20
Co^{2+}	2	15	8	21
Ni^{2+}	2	16	8	22
Cu^+	1	18	8	23
Zn^{2+}	2	18	8	24
Ag^+	1	18	18	28
Cd^{2+}	2	18	18	29

$\text{X} = \text{F, Cl, Br, I}$) are calculated from the SK variational method. The resultant vdw constants C and D have been evaluated from eqs. (9) and (10) respectively.

Total Van der Waals energies, W_v , for these crystals have been calculated using the values of C and D obtained (i) in the present study, (ii) due to Bakhshi *et al.* and (iii) due to May, Mayer and Levy and it is found that the present values of W_v are larger than those of Bakhshi *et al.* and May, Mayer and Levy (Table 1). The reason for the differences between the results of the present work and other investigators are due to the effective number of

Table 3. Values of Van der Waals energies, W_v , (kcal mol⁻⁶) and crystal energies, W , (kcal mol⁻¹) based on three different interionic force models

Crystal	-W												Expt.
	-W _v			Ali-Hasan			Born-Mayer			Hellmann			
	(i)	(ii)	(iii)	(i)	(ii)	(iii)	(i)	(ii)	(iii)	(i)	(ii)	(iii)	
CuCl	84.9	67.5	15.2	228.0	224.4	214.8	226.4	223.1	214.1	225.1	222.0	213.7	232.0
CuBr	93.8	64.8	15.2	220.4	214.8	205.4	218.9	213.4	204.7	217.3	212.5	204.3	227.9
CuI	89.8	62.8	17.4	215.9	209.5	199.0	214.3	208.3	198.4	213.3	207.6	198.2	225.8
AgF	57.1	-	-	233.0	-	-	232.0	-	-	232.0	-	-	225.4
AgCl	69.8	51.9	28.7	210.0	206.2	201.2	209.0	205.1	200.4	207.8	204.5	200.1	213.6
AgBr	81.2	53.1	28.4	205.6	199.4	194.1	104.1	198.3	193.3	203.1	197.7	193.0	210.2
AgI	79.5	54.0	30.1	197.6	192.0	187.0	196.2	190.9	186.2	195.2	190.2	185.9	208.1
TlCl	59.1	47.6	27.4	171.1	168.8	165.2	170.0	167.8	164.5	169.0	167.0	164.0	172.8
TlBr	69.4	49.2	27.7	170.1	166.4	162.4	168.9	165.5	161.6	167.9	164.7	161.2	169.1
TlI	68.3	49.6	-	168.0	164.4	-	167.6	163.4	-	166.8	163.0	-	163.6
Average				2.6	4.1	7.6	2.9	4.5	8.0	3.3	4.9	8.1	

%deviation

(i) Calculated in the present study using new values of C and D .

(ii) Calculate using the values of C and D of Bakhshi *et al.*

(iii) Calculated using the values of C and D of May, Mayer and Levy.

electrons in the ions. Now to assess the merit of the newly calculated values of C and D , we compute the values of crystal energy, W , using the new values of C and D , in which the short the short-range repulsive potential $V_{sr}(r)$ of Born-Mayer, Hellmann and Ali-Hasan are taken and the results obtained by three different interionic force models are compared with the experimental values⁸ in Table 3. We have also calculated values of crystal energy using the values of C and D of Bakhshi *et al.* and May, Mayer and Levy based on the three different models and the result so obtained are reported Table 3.

A careful examination of Table 3 exhibits the remarkable agreement for the crystal energies, calculated using the new values of C and D , based on Ali-Hasan model with the experimental values. It is also seen that Ali-Hasan model gives better results of crystal energies either using the present values of C and D or the values of C and D of Bakhshi *et al.* and May, Mayer and Levy. The suitability of this model is also fairly observed in the analysis of molecular as well as crystal binding in (i) alkali halides^{12,13} and (ii) alkali hydrides¹⁴.

Furthermore, we observe that there exists the discrepancy between the theoretical and experimental results of crystal energy for copper and silver halides. This is due to the fact that these halides are partially covalent character in nature on account of the outermost d -electrons

present in Cu^+ and Ag^+ . The crystal energy of thallium halides obtained from various interionic force models using the vdw potentials of Bakhshi *et al.* and May, Mayer and Levy are much lower than the experimental data except in case of TlI for which the agreement is very satisfactory. The application of new values of dipole-dipole and dipole-quadrupole co-efficients for ion pair interactions to predict the elastic constants of the mixed crystal AgCl-AgBr will be our next step of study.

Acknowledgement

We are extremely grateful to Prof. M. Hasan for his keen interest in completion of this work. We are thankful to the Head and staffs of the University Department of T. M. Bhagalpur University also for providing necessary environment. We are thankful to the referee for his useful suggestions.

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